

THE EFFECT OF NEURONS AS A REGULATOR OF THE EATING BEHAVIOR OF DIGESTIVE NATURAL MICROFLORA EXISTENCE OF CATTLE

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Biology is the study of the life of living organisms, including their structure, function, growth, origin, evolution and distribution. Biology is the science of life. Biology has many branches of disciplines which among the branches of science can be interconnected to produce a new research, for example in microbiology and animal physiology. Microbiology is a branch of the biological discipline that studies microscopic organisms, while animal physiology is the study of the mechanical, physical, and biochemical functions of animals. By merging these two disciplines, I hope to discover whether the neuron-regulated feeding behavior of cattle can influence the presence of the natural digestive microflora.

The level of maturity affects the digestive system of cows. The more mature the cow, the more perfect the digestive system. Feed is very important in the growth and development of cattle. The quality and quantity of food and the ways in which it is given greatly affect the ability of cattle to produce. The development of ruminants in Indonesia is faced with the potential constraints of feed resources that are not in accordance with the quantity, quality, and continuity. Therefore, its handling needs serious attention because feed is one of the important factors in livestock business. Therefore, improving feed management is expected to increase the efficiency of beef cattle business (Mahaputra et al., 2003).

Feeding is regulated by perception in the hypothalamus, particularly the first-order arcuate nucleus (ARC) neurons, of the body's energy state (Kurita et.al., 2015). PVN is a feeding regulation center in the brain (Schwartz et.al., 2000). It consists of neurons expressing neuropeptides including arginine vasopressin (AVP), corticotropin-releasing hormone (CRH), oxytocin (Oxt), and nucleobindin-2/nesfatin-1 (NUCB2/Nesf-1), all of which have been implicated in feeding suppression (Pei et.al., 2014). To explore the brain region targeted by FGF21, we investigated c-Fos expression in the areas of the hypothalamus and brain stem implicated in feeding. ICV injection of FGF21 significantly increased c-Fos expression in the suprachiasmatic nucleus (SCN), PVN, dorsomedial hypothalamus (DMH), and nucleus tractus solitarius (NTS), confirming previous report that FGF21 increased c-Fos in PVN. Among these four regions, the increment of c-Fos expression was outstandingly high (five-fold) in PVN,

suggesting that the anorexigenic effect of FGF21 could involve PVN (Santoso, 2017).

Based on the research of Hasana, Nurmiati, and Periadnadi (2015) the presence of natural bacteria in the digestive tract of beef cattle can be seen by the presence and activity of bacteria indicated by the halo area formed on SMA medium, modified GPA, APB and CMC Agar as bacterial hydrolysis against proteolytic, fermentative, amylolytic and cellulolytic. There are 3 kinds of microbes found in the rumen fluid, namely bacteria, protozoa, and a small number of fungi. The total microbial volume is estimated to cover 3.60% of the rumen fluid (Wanapat et al., 2011). Bacteria are the largest number of microflora while protozoa are fewer. Fungi are found in grazing cattle and function in the rumen as a cellulolytic group (Guo et al., 2010). Cellulose is one of the crude fiber fractions of plants that is very difficult/cannot be digested by animal digestive enzymes, as an energy source for microorganisms in the rumen. In order to be used by rumen microbes, cellulose must first be broken down into compounds with low molecular weight, such as mono-, di-, and tri-saccharides. The degradation involves the cellulase enzyme complex produced by microbes. The cellulose fraction is the largest component as a constituent of mature plant cell walls, which is around 40-50% (Wainwright, 2002). According to Orpin and Joblin (1988), most plant polysaccharides are fermented by fungi in the rumen and almost 50% of the cellulose and hemicellulose components of plants are digested by fungi, while *Ruminococcus albus* bacteria are only able to digest 8%.

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